

Multimodal neuro-nanotechnology: new paradigm or renewed unfulfilled promises?

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In a recent perspective in PNAS entitled *Multimodal neuro-nanotechnology: Challenging the existing paradigm in glioblastoma therapy*, Kudruk et al argue that two technologies, adhesive dextran-dendrimer hydrogels (Artzi lab) and spherical nucleic acids (Mirkin lab), should be combined to address the challenge of treating glioblastoma patients, eventually with the addition of minimally invasive surgery (focused ultrasound, laser interstitial thermal therapy) (1).

I have followed for 15 years the development of spherical nucleic acids (SNAs) asking critical questions in particular about the extent of their access to the cytosol (2–4), which is essential for many of their proposed applications. SNAs to detect mRNAs in live cells were commercialised as SmartFlares, and distributed by Merck Millipore (now MilliporeSigma) for 5 years, but were withdrawn in 2018. We, and others (2–6), had shown that they did not in fact detect mRNAs. The full history of SNAs will be written elsewhere, but the clinical developments have not been more successful than the intracellular mRNA detection. Thus Kudruk et al’s presentation of SNAs as a “powerful class of nanotherapeutics” is misleading.

The company Aurasense was founded by Mirkin, Thaxton and Giljohann in 2009. It later became Exicure with the mission to develop the biomedical applications of SNAs. It has not been a success (figure 1). In spite of many hundreds of millions of dollars from research grants and private investors, and of partnerships with big pharmaceutical companies announced as being worth over a billion dollars (Purdue, 2016, “up to \$790M to develop Psoriasis treatment”; IPSEN, 2021, “eligible to receive up to \$1B” for the development of treatments of regenerative disorders (7, 8)), Exicure failed to deliver a single drug.

Figure 1: Stock price (NASDAQ) of spherical nucleic acids company Exicure, Inc. (XCUR), 15 July 2024

In November 2021, Exicure announced that a senior researcher had committed research improprieties with respect to their preclinical program for the treatment of Friedreich’s Ataxia. Documents released in the context of a related securities class action allege that not only data had been fabricated but also that safety concerns had been neglected (significant toxicity observed in animal experiments) (9). All research and development at Exicure have stopped, but Mirkin, Margolin and Teplensky have founded a new company, Flashpoint Therapeutics, apparently with similar goals.

In their PNAS opinion, Kudruk et al mention the clinical trial of Cavrotolimod (NCT03684785) and indicate a 33% overall response rate at the highest dosage. No reference is provided but the figure

appears to come from an interim report presented by the company (press release and presentation at a conference (10)). The 33% are in fact 2 patients from a sub-group of 6 patients. The clinical trial did not go to completion: it was stopped for administrative reasons in the aftermath of the fraud case mentioned above.

Public and private funders of scientific research in academia and start-up companies have to make choices about which biomedical technologies or innovative therapies they sponsor. The scientific literature plays a critical role in informing those decisions and must therefore be balanced and accurate.

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